

Sorption of pyrene and fluoranthene onto common microplastics under freshwater conditions

Sara Exojo-Trujillo, Laura Higuera-Contreras, Pilar Hernández-Muñoz, Rafael Gavara*

Packaging group, Instituto de Agroquímica y Tecnología de Alimentos, CSIC, Av. Agustín Escardino 7, 46980 Paterna (Valencia), Spain.

Email addresses: saetru@iata.csic.es, lahicon@iata.csic.es, phernan@iata.csic.es and rgavara@iata.csic.es

Supplementary file

S1. Materials

This work has been carried out focusing on two polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), pyrene (PYR) and fluoranthene (FLU). These organic compounds consist solely of carbon and hydrogen atoms, and their structures are composed of two or more fused benzene rings, which confer the characteristic properties summarised in **Table S1**.

Table S1. Chemical structure and relevant data of the target polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons.

PAH	Chemical structure	CAS	Log K _{ow} ^a	b.p. (°C) ^b	Density (g cm ⁻³)
PYR		129-00-0	4.88	404.0	1.271
FLU		206-44-0	5.16	384.0	1.120

^a K_{ow}: Octanol-water partition coefficient, (Explore Chemistry, <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>)

^b b. p.: boiling point

The microplastics used in this study are common materials used in various applications, including packaging and textile sectors. Their sources are described in **Table S2**.

24 **Table S2.** Materials and suppliers used as microplastics.

PA MXD6	Aromatic-type polyamide	MITSUBISHI Gas Chemical Europe GmbH, Dusseldorf, Germany
HDPE	high-density polyethylene	ELITE, Dow, Tarragona, Spain
LDPE	low-density polyethylene	Sigma-Aldrich
PP	polypropylene	ExxonMobil™ PP1013H1, Exxonmobil Europe, Machelen, Belgium)
PLA	polylactic acid	Luminy LX175, Total Energies Corbion, Oss, The Netherlands)
PET	polyethylene terephthalate	Selar PT, Dupont Ibérica, Barcelona, Spain

25

26 **S2. Chromatographic analysis**

27 Analytes concentrations were determined by using a 7890B gas chromatography (GC) equipped
 28 with a flame ionization detector (FID) (Agilent Technologies Spain, Las Rozas de Madrid, Spain),
 29 and an HP-5 column (diameter 30 x 0.32 mm, and film thickness 0.25 µm). The oven temperature
 30 programme was set to ramp from 80 °C (held 1 min) to 240 °C (held 5 min) at 15 °C min⁻¹. The
 31 inlet temperature was maintained at 270 °C and injections were performed in splitless mode (1.2
 32 min). The carrier gas was helium, and it was set at a constant flow rate of 1 mL·min⁻¹.

33 The microextraction procedure of the analytes was carried out with a previously conditioned
 34 polydimethylsiloxane/divinylbenzene (PDMS/DVB) solid-phase microextraction (SPME) fibre
 35 with 65 µm film thickness (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany).

36 The SPME fibre was immersed for 40 minutes in the measurement solution, previously adjusted
 37 to pH 10 with a 5M NaOH solution (an optimized condition to improve analyte retention on the
 38 fibre), keeping the solution magnetically stirred. Subsequently, thermal desorption of the
 39 compounds retained in the fibre was carried out in the GC injector at 270 °C (inlet temperature)
 40 for 5 min.

41 **S3. Microplastics Characterization**

42 *S3.1. Scanning electron microscopy and elemental analysis*

43 Particle morphology was examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (SCIOS 2 FIB-
 44 SEM, ThermoFisher Scientific) operated at an acceleration voltage of 3kV. Samples were placed
 45 on a carbon sheet and sputter-coated with gold for 30 s. **Figure S1** presents the images obtained
 46 by SEM for all the microparticles selected. The elemental composition of samples was obtained

47 using an elemental analyser (Flashmart, Thermofisher Scientific). The results of the elemental
48 analysis of the microplastic (MP) samples are provided in **Table S3**.

49
50 **Figure S1.** SEM images of PA MXD6, HDPE, LDPE, PP, PLA, and PET microfragments.

51 The specific surface area of the particles was estimated by correcting the theoretical value using
 52 a factor that accounts for surface roughness (Berrezueta et al., 2019). For this correction, the
 53 normalized perimeter-to-area ratio (normalized PoA or Ψ) was applied, acting as a two-
 54 dimensional analogue. To calculate the Ψ parameter for the MPs under study, the perimeter (P_i)
 55 and area (A_i) of each particle ($n = 50$) were obtained from the two-dimensional representations of
 56 SEM images. The Ψ values were then calculated using the following equation:

$$\Psi = \frac{P_i}{2\sqrt{\pi A_i}} \quad (\text{S1})$$

57 **Table S3.** Elemental composition of MPs.

MP	% O	% N	% C	10^{-3} O+N/C
PA MXD6	12.620 ± 0.028	11.215 ± 0.092	67.345 ± 0.007	353.924 ± 0.908
HDPE	0.120 ± 0.014	0.000 ± 0.000	85.770 ± 0.792	1.398 ± 0.152
LDPE	0.220 ± 0.071	0.045 ± 0.007	85.675 ± 0.035	3.093 ± 0.744
PP	0.380 ± 0.028	0.020 ± 0.028	85.385 ± 0.064	4.685 ± 0.003
PLA	43.190 ± 0.156	0.220 ± 0.057	50.910 ± 0.240	852.681 ± 0.140
PET	26.030 ± 0.184	0.040 ± 0.000	65.360 ± 0.042	398.868 ± 3.072

58

59 *S3.2. FTIR analysis*

60 The functional groups present on the surface of the MPs were identified using a JASCO 4100
 61 FTIR spectrometer (Jasco, Easton, MD) with a single-reflection attenuated total reflectance
 62 (ATR) accessory (ZnSe crystal, PIKE Technologies, USA). The FTIR spectra were recorded in
 63 the 600-4000 cm^{-1} range. **Figure S2** shows the FTIR spectra of the analysed samples.

64 The spectra of all tested materials showed the peaks corresponding to the asymmetric and
 65 symmetric C-H stretching vibrations over 2850 and 2900 cm^{-1} , respectively, and the characteristic
 66 bending deformation peak at 1470 cm^{-1} . As shown in the FTIR spectra of the aromatic polymers,
 67 PA MXD6 and PET presented peaks assigned to the in-plane C-H bending within aromatic rings.
 68 In the PA MXD6 spectrum, peaks were observed at 1025 and 1040 cm^{-1} , indicative of 1,3-
 69 aromatic substitution). These peaks were shifted to 1015 and 1095 cm^{-1} in the PET spectrum,
 70 indicative of 1,4 aromatic substitution.

71 As shown by the FTIR spectra of PLA, PET and PA-MXD6, stretching vibration peaks of C=O
 72 appeared at wavenumbers of 1600-1700 cm^{-1} . In the case of polyamide, this signal appeared at
 73 lower wavenumbers (around 1630 cm^{-1}) compared to PET and PLA, due to the appearance of the
 74 amide functionality. Finally, two peaks were observed at 1245 and 3267 cm^{-1} in this FTIR spectra,

75 corresponding to the N atom bonds. The first peak is attributed to C-N stretching and the second
76 to N-H stretching.

77
78 **Figure S2.** Fourier transformation infrared (FTIR) spectra of the selected microparticulated
79 materials.

80

81 *S3.3. Thermal analysis*

82 The thermal behaviour was analysed using Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC Q2000, TA
83 Instruments, USA) with a heating ramp from -25 to 300 °C under a N₂ purge. Synthetic polymeric
84 materials are at least partially amorphous, and their amorphous regions may exhibit either a glassy
85 or rubbery state depending on the glass transition temperature (T_g). T_g values are shown in **Table**
86 **1**. The T_g of HDPE, LDPE and PP could not be determined experimentally under the applied
87 conditions, as their reported values are below the operational limit of the equipment (-25 °C for
88 PP and -100 °C for both polyethylenes) (Greene, 2021). Based on the observed DSC endotherms,
89 degree of crystallinity of the materials was estimated from the melting enthalpies obtained using
90 the following equation:

$$X_C(\%) = \frac{\Delta H_m - \Delta H_{CC}}{\Delta H_m^0} \times 100 \quad (\text{S2})$$

91 where ΔH_m and ΔH_m^0 are the experimental melting enthalpies of each sample and that of the fully
92 crystalline material, respectively, and ΔH_{CC} is the cold crystallization enthalpy. The ΔH_m^0 values

93 for the studied materials were, 175.00 J·g⁻¹ for PA MXD6 (Doudou et al., 2006), 280.00 J·g⁻¹ for
94 both polyethylenes (Li et al., 2019), 198.00 J·g⁻¹ for PP (Shafigullin et al., 2018), 93.70 J·g⁻¹ for
95 PLA (Zhang et al., 2018) and 135.98 J·g⁻¹ for PET (Starkweather et al., 1983). The materials
96 ranked in decreasing order of crystallinity were: HDPE > PA MXD6 > PP > PLA > LDPE >
97 PET.

98 **S4. Sorption Isotherms**

99 Equilibrium sorption data of PAHs onto the seven types of MPs at various sorbate concentrations
100 were fitted to four adsorption models: Linear, Freundlich, Langmuir and Temkin.

101 **Figures S3 to S6** show the fitting of the 4 isotherm models for both PYR and FLU using the
102 linearised forms of equations (2), (3), (4) and (5). The values for the parameters for the four
103 isotherm models are presented in **Table S4**, together with the correlation coefficient values (R²).

104

105 **Figure S3.** Experimental sorption data (dots) and their fitting to Henry's model (eq. (2), lines).

106 (A), PYR; (B), FLU.

107

108 **Figure S4.** Experimental sorption data (dots) and their fitting to Langmuir's model (eq. (3), lines).
 109 (A), PYR; (B), FLU.

110

111 **Figure S5.** Experimental sorption data (dots) and their fitting to Freundlich's model (eq. (4),
 112 lines). (A), PYR; (B), FLU.

113

114 **Figure S6.** Experimental sorption data (dots) and their fitting to Temkin's model (eq. (5), lines).

115 (A), PYR; (B), FLU.

116

117 **Table S4.** Parameters calculated with different models for sorption of PYR and FLU onto MPs.

MPs	Linear model		Freundlich model			Langmuir model			Temkin model			
	K_H (L m ⁻²)	R ²	K_F (L m ⁻²)	n_F	R ²	K_L (L μg ⁻¹)	q_{max} (μg m ⁻²)	R ²	$b_T \cdot q_{max}$ (J g mol ⁻¹ μg ⁻¹)	K_T	R ²	
PYR	PA	94±8	0.966	50.6±1.7	0.82±0.15	0.909	-0.023±0.015	-2605±2310	0.298	2.68±0.89	0.0673±0.0230	0.751
	MXD6											
	PP	59±8	0.919	4.7±1.8	0.53±0.07	0.956	-0.036±0.005	-562±178	0.768	2.27±0.58	0.0149±0.0015	0.837
	PLA	46±3	0.981	22.1±1.7	0.77±0.13	0.919	-0.025±0.014	-1293±963	0.376	5.17±1.10	0.0531±0.0088	0.881
	PET	57±4	0.983	6.5±2.0	0.57±0.08	0.959	-0.029±0.008	-794±448	0.611	2.31±0.14	0.0148±0.0004	0.992
	HDPE	530±34	0.980	161.5±1.3	0.58±0.06	0.965	-0.116±0.023	-1645±642	0.667	1.03±0.07	0.4008±0.0634	0.988
LDPE	746±72	0.964	516.7±1.9	0.81±0.31	0.780	-0.048±0.077	-11379±22529	0.113	0.72±0.26	0.3547±0.2577	0.789	
FLU	PA	60±2	0.997	43.7±1.1	0.90±0.02	0.999	-0.009±0.001	-5322±503	0.974	3.54±0.50	0.0494±0.0058	0.944
	MXD6											
	PP	84±5	0.987	29.0±1.2	0.72±0.04	0.994	-0.024±0.004	-2155±520	0.896	2.07±0.21	0.0282±0.0016	0.980
	PLA	23±2	0.978	60.0±1.2	1.42±0.22	0.976	-0.036±0.010	1215±196	0.950	9.80±0.72	0.1282±0.0194	0.989
	PET	49±4	0.980	184.6±1.2	1.74±0.22	0.969	0.045±0.026	2247±688	0.842	5.06±1.19	0.1838±0.1177	0.900
	HDPE	827±81	0.963	693.9±2.0	0.90±0.41	0.708	-0.033±0.101	-20481±72816	0.038	0.77±0.28	0.5621±0.9022	0.792
LDPE	1114±149	0.918	379.3±2.1	0.46±0.19	0.667	-0.256±0.078	-1457±1086	0.375	0.54±0.22	0.5545±0.5073	0.664	

118

S5. Kinetic models applicable to the sorption of PAHs molecules in microplastics.

Figure S7. Experimental PAHs sorption evolution with time in 6 MPs exposed to $50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (empty dots) and $100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (full dots): A) PYR; B) FLU.

S5.1 Solutions to the Fick's second law for spheres.

Eq. (6) was used to obtain the theoretical evolution of concentration of a sorbate substance in a sphere. For calculations, the sphere radius was divided in 50 parts ($\delta R = 1/50 = 0.02$). The smaller the finite element for time (δT), the better estimation of the diffusion is obtained but the larger the calculation time. To avoid fluctuations the maximum value for δT should be $\delta T < 0.5 \delta R^2$ (Crank, 1975). Thus, the maximum value for δT in this work was 0.0002 and our selection was 0.0001. The concentrations at each $i\delta R$ point from 0 to 1 (from axis to external surface) at times ranging from 0 to 1 were obtained and are shown in **Figure S8**.

Figure S8. Relative concentration evolution of a sorbate in a sphere of radio "a".

The amount of sorbate present in the sphere can be calculated by summation of the quantities of substance present in the spherical crown volume limited by $(i+1)\delta R$ and $i\delta R$, according to equation (S3).

$$\frac{q_t}{q_e} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{c(t)}{c(\infty)} \cdot \frac{4\pi}{3} (R_{i+1}^3 - R_i^3) \quad (\text{S3})$$

This profile is presented in **Figure S9**.

Figure S9. Relative sorption of a contaminant in a spherical particle of radius " a " obtained by solving eq. (6) by finite elements approach (symbols) and the result of curve fitting (red line).

This curve represents the universal sorption profile of a sorbate through a spheric particle assuming that initially the sorbate is 0 in the sphere and that the diffusion coefficient is constant and independent of time or contaminant concentration. This profile was fitted by a 4-parameter exponential rise-to-maximum function with a regression of 1.000 and standard error 0.005 using the Dynamic curve fitting procedure provided by Sigmaplot 14.5 (Anonymous, 2024).

Table S5 presents the equilibrium concentrations of PYR in LDPE MPs exposed to a simulated freshwater solution containing initially 50 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of PYR (expressed both per unit of mass and per unit of surface area) and the Fickian diffusion coefficient values obtained through this theoretical approach.

Table S5. Sorption of PYR at equilibrium (q_e) expressed in (μg of PYR/g of MP) and in (μg of PYR/ m^2 of MP) on LDPE microparticles of various dimensions, and value of the Fick's diffusion coefficient for the sorption process obtained by fitting of eq. (8).

Average diameter	q_e ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	q_e ($\mu\text{g/m}^2$)	$10^{14} \cdot D$ (m^2/s)
80	474 ± 5^a	3350 ± 840^a	3.2 ± 1.7^a
120	385 ± 7^b	4080 ± 680^a	10.7 ± 4.5^b
160	336 ± 10^c	4750 ± 590^a	14.8 ± 5.6^b
220	193 ± 3^d	3750 ± 340^a	30.4 ± 5.2^c

^{a,b,...} different letters indicate significant differences between microparticle sizes

Figure S10 to S15 show the experimental sorption data obtained for PYR and FLU into diverse microparticles and the fitting curve obtained with the D value obtained with the Solver tool and equation (7). **Table S6** includes the D values obtained for the diverse samples (PAHs and MPs).

Figure S10. Sorption kinetics of PYR and FLU from aqueous solutions at 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in LDPE microparticles: experimental data (symbols) and the fitting curves obtained from eq. (8) and the D values collected in Table S6.

Figure S11. Sorption kinetics of PYR and FLU from aqueous solutions at 50 and 100 µg/L in HDPE microparticles: experimental data (symbols) and the fitting curves obtained from eq. (8) and the D values collected in Table S6.

Figure S12. Sorption kinetics of PYR and FLU from aqueous solutions at 50 and 100 µg/L in PP microparticles: experimental data (symbols) and the fitting curves obtained from eq. (8) and the D values collected in Table S6.

Figure S13. Sorption kinetics of PYR and FLU from aqueous solutions at 50 and 100 µg/L in PA-MXD6 microparticles: experimental data (symbols) and the fitting curves obtained from eq. (8) and the D values collected in Table S6.

Figure S14. Sorption kinetics of PYR and FLU from aqueous solutions at 50 and 100 µg/L in PLA microparticles: experimental data (symbols) and the fitting curves obtained from eq. (8) and the D values collected in Table S6.

Figure S15. Sorption kinetics of PYR and FLU from aqueous solutions at 50 and 100 µg/L in PET microparticles: experimental data (symbols) and the fitting curves obtained from eq. (8) and the D values collected in Table S6.

Table S6. Data obtained by curve fitting of the experimental data to equation (8): q_e ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2$) is the concentration at equilibrium of the contaminant in the MPs, and D the diffusion coefficient value for each contaminant, initial concentration of exposure and type of MPs.

Polymer	C ($\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$)	PYRENE		FLUORANTHENE	
		q_e ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2$)	$10^{14} \cdot D$ (m^2/s)	q_e ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2$)	$10^{14} \cdot D$ (m^2/s)
LDPE	50	4291 ± 60	32.0 ± 2.4	4396 ± 54	26.6 ± 1.3
	100	8604 ± 113	14.9 ± 0.8	8342 ± 94	11.8 ± 1.3
HDPE	50	4114 ± 71	18.3 ± 1.1	3944 ± 51	11.5 ± 0.5
	100	7903 ± 94	16.6 ± 7.6	7649 ± 105	15.7 ± 8.0
PP	50	1771 ± 77	8.2 ± 0.4	1468 ± 81	9.0 ± 0.9
	100	3361 ± 40	14.9 ± 0.8	3194 ± 109	$11.4 \pm 1,3$
PA-MXD6	50	1369 ± 52	18.0 ± 2.8	1324 ± 42	9.4 ± 0.5
	100	2323 ± 32	16.5 ± 0.7	2419 ± 86	18.2 ± 2.1
PLA	50	1242 ± 29	4.8 ± 0.4	1280 ± 59	12.6 ± 2.1
	100	2238 ± 65	18.0 ± 1.8	2139 ± 7	27.0 ± 0.5
PET	50	1235 ± 6	7.2 ± 0.1	1460 ± 14	6.8 ± 0.2
	100	2323 ± 45	13.8 ± 0.6	2923 ± 161	7.5 ± 0.7

S5.2 Solutions to the diffusion of the aromatic molecules through a boundary layer

Figure S16. Sorption kinetics of PYR and FLU onto PLA at 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Experimental data (symbols) and theoretical fits (lines) using eq (11) and (15), with the parameter's values included in legend.

Figure S17. Sorption kinetics of PYR and FLU onto PET at 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Experimental data (symbols) and theoretical fits (lines) using eq (11) and (15), with the parameter's values included in legend.

Figure S18. Sorption kinetics of PYR and FLU onto PP at 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Experimental data (symbols) and theoretical fits (lines) using eq (11) and (15), with the parameter's values included in legend.

Figure S19. Sorption kinetics of PYR and FLU onto HDPE at 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Experimental data (symbols) and theoretical fits (lines) using eq (11) and (15), with the parameter's values included in legend.

Figure S20. Sorption kinetics of PYR and FLU onto LDPE at 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Experimental data (symbols) and theoretical fits (lines) using eq (11) and (15), with the parameter's values included in legend.

S5.3 Empirical models

The fitting of empirical kinetic models has been obtained by considering the q_e value as the average of the retention after 20 hours of exposure, since apparently, equilibrium has been already achieved. Several studies mentioned about the convenience of removing data close to equilibrium in the modelling of kinetics since these values might infer wrong results (Revellame et al., 2020). However, the fitting of this model using the linear form provided poor results, with low regression coefficient values and equilibrium concentrations deviating substantially from the experimental data, deficiencies also observed by others (Mohan et al., 2006; Zhang et al., 2020).

As an example, **Figure S21** shows the curves obtained by linear fitting for three MPs, PA-MXD6 and HDPE using linear and exponential form of eq. (16). As can be seen, although good match with experimental data was obtained for HDPE, for others, the fitting failed in both the profile and the equilibrium concentrations.

Figure S21. PYR sorption kinetics on PA-MXD6 and HDPE: Comparison of the fitting quality.

To solve this issue, data were fitted to an exponential-rising-to-a-maximum equation using non-linear regression tools of Sigmaplot, in agreement with other reports that questioned the reliability of the linearised form (Fung et al., 2023; Revellame et al., 2020). This approach yielded good fits for all PAH/MP systems and improved accuracy relative to linear regression. **Figure S22** to **S27** display the non-linear fitting, while **Tables S7** summarise the fitting values of q_e and k_l . Other reports found that PFO describe the sorption of organic compounds in PVC and PS (Liu et al., 2019).

Figure S22. Kinetic data for the sorption of pyrene (A) and fluoranthene (B) in PA-MXD6 microparticles. Experimental data in exposure to 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (dots), and the results of curve fitting to Pseudo-First Order (PFO) and Pseudo-Second Order (PSO) models (lines).

Figure S23. Kinetic data for the sorption of pyrene (A) and fluoranthene (B) in HDPE microparticles. Experimental data in exposure to 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (dots), and the results of curve fitting to Pseudo-First Order (PFO) and Pseudo-Second Order (PSO) models (lines).

Figure S24. Kinetic data for the sorption of pyrene (A) and fluoranthene (B) in LDPE microparticles. Experimental data in exposure to 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (dots), and the results of curve fitting to Pseudo-First Order (PFO) and Pseudo-Second Order (PSO) models (lines).

Figure S25. Kinetic data for the sorption of pyrene (A) and fluoranthene (B) in PP microparticles. Experimental data in exposure to 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (dots), and the results of curve fitting to Pseudo-First Order (PFO) and Pseudo-Second Order (PSO) models (lines).

Figure S26. Kinetic data for the sorption of pyrene (A) and fluoranthene (B) in PLA microparticles. Experimental data in exposure to 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (dots), and the results of curve fitting to Pseudo-First Order (PFO) and Pseudo-Second Order (PSO) models (lines).

Figure S27. Kinetic data for the sorption of pyrene (A) and fluoranthene (B) in PET microparticles. Experimental data in exposure to 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (dots), and the results of curve fitting to Pseudo-First Order (PFO) and Pseudo-Second Order (PSO) models (lines).

Table S7. Parameters of the pseudo-first order model obtained by fitting using eq. (16) and represented in **Figure S22 to S27**. q_e values are expressed in ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) and k_1 in (h^{-1}).

MPs	PYRENE (50 $\mu\text{g/L}$)				PYRENE (100 $\mu\text{g/L}$)			
	$q_{e, \text{exp}}$	k_1	q_e	R^2	$q_{e, \text{exp}}$	k_1	q_e	R^2
PA MXD6	1369 ± 52	0.95 ± 0.10	1334 ± 27	0.987	2323 ± 32	0.84 ± 0.06	2286 ± 34	0.992
HDPE	4114 ± 71	0.84 ± 0.04	4125 ± 39	0.997	7903 ± 94	0.74 ± 0.06	7982 ± 152	0.987
LDPE	4291 ± 60	1.53 ± 0.15	4219 ± 55	0.992	8604 ± 113	0.60 ± 0.03	8641 ± 98	0.996
PP	1771 ± 77	0.47 ± 0.06	1762 ± 60	0.965	3361 ± 40	0.82 ± 0.16	3281 ± 131	0.941
PLA	1242 ± 29	0.33 ± 0.03	1238 ± 30	0.987	2238 ± 65	0.87 ± 0.06	2227 ± 30	0.993
PET	1235 ± 6	0.39 ± 0.07	1238 ± 30	0.954	2323 ± 45	0.66 ± 0.03	2328 ± 24	0.997
MPs	FLUORANTHENE (50 $\mu\text{g/L}$)				FLUORANTHENE (100 $\mu\text{g/L}$)			
	$q_{e, \text{exp}}$	k_1	q_e	R^2	$q_{e, \text{exp}}$	k_1	q_e	R^2
PA MXD6	1324 ± 42	0.48 ± 0.05	1328 ± 40	0.973	2419 ± 86	1.04 ± 0.19	2376 ± 79	0.956
HDPE	3944 ± 51	0.54 ± 0.05	3993 ± 51	0.983	7649 ± 105	0.71 ± 0.04	7708 ± 99	0.994
LDPE	4396 ± 54	1.16 ± 0.03	4397 ± 18	0.999	8342 ± 94	1.26 ± 0.08	8244 ± 85	0.995
PP	1468 ± 81	0.49 ± 0.04	1469 ± 33	0.985	3194 ± 109	0.63 ± 0.10	3142 ± 121	0.950
PLA	1280 ± 59	0.54 ± 0.07	1303 ± 48	0.961	2139 ± 7	1.22 ± 0.03	2129 ± 8	0.999
PET	1460 ± 14	0.37 ± 0.05	1477 ± 59	0.961	2923 ± 161	0.46 ± 0.04	2921 ± 73	0.982

Figure S28 to S33 display the linearised PSO model for the seven polymer materials under study and **Table 4** collects the parameters obtained from eq. (17).

Figure S28. Plot of the sorption data for PA-MXD6 microparticles following the linear representation of the pseudo-second order model (eq.(17)).

Figure S29. Plot of the sorption data for HDPE microparticles following the linear representation of the pseudo-second order model eq.(17)).

Figure S30. Plot of the sorption data for LDPE microparticles following the linear representation of the pseudo-second order model (eq.(17)).

Figure S31. Plot of the sorption data for PP microparticles following the linear representation of the pseudo-second order model (eq.(17)).

Figure S32. Plot of the sorption data for PLA microparticles following the linear representation of the pseudo-second order model (eq.(17)).

Figure S33. Plot of the sorption data for PET microparticles following the linear representation of the pseudo-second order model (eq.(17)).

References

- Anonymous, 2024. S4U [WWW Document]. SigmaPlot Curve Fitting and Regression. URL <https://www.solutions4u-asia.com/PDT/SYSTAT/sigmaplot/SPlot-CurveFitting.html> (accessed 2.19.24).
- Azizian, S., 2004. Kinetic models of sorption: A theoretical analysis. *J Colloid Interface Sci* 276, 47–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2004.03.048>
- Berrezueta, E., Cuervas-Mons, J., Rodríguez-Rey, Á., Ordóñez-Casado, B., 2019. Representativity of 2D shape parameters for mineral particles in quantitative petrography. *Minerals* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3390/min9120768>
- Chang, C.K., Tun, H., Chen, C.C., 2020. An activity-based formulation for Langmuir adsorption isotherm. *Adsorption* 26, 375–386. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10450-019-00185-4>
- Crank, J., 1975. *The Mathematics of Diffusion*, Second. ed. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Doudou, B.B., Dargent, E., Grenet, J., 2006. Crystallization and melting behaviour of PA MXD6. *J Therm Anal Calorim* 85, 409–415. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-005-7299-y>
- Fung, Y.H., Han, J., Tam, N.F.Y., Chen, J., Chan, S.M.N., Cheung, S.G., Zhou, H.C., Lo, C.M., Ma, Y., 2023. Different sorption behaviours of pyrene onto polyethylene microplastics in a binary system with water and a ternary system with water and sediment. *Environ Technol Innov* 30, 103086. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ETI.2023.103086>
- Greene, J.P., 2021. Microstructures of Polymers, in: *Automotive Plastics and Composites: Materials and Processing*. Andrew, William, pp. 27–39.
- Ho, Y.S., Mckay, G., 1999. Pseudo-second order model for sorption processes, *Process Biochemistry*.
- Li, D., Zhou, L., Wang, X., He, L., Yang, X., 2019. Effect of crystallinity of polyethylene with different densities on breakdown strength and conductance property. *Materials* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma12111746>
- Liu, G., Zhu, Z., Yang, Y., Sun, Y., Yu, F., Ma, J., 2019. Sorption behavior and mechanism of hydrophilic organic chemicals to virgin and aged microplastics in freshwater and seawater. *Environmental Pollution* 246, 26–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVPOL.2018.11.100>

- Millot, C., Fillot, L.A., Lame, O., Sotta, P., Seguela, R., 2015. Assessment of polyamide-6 crystallinity by DSC: Temperature dependence of the melting enthalpy. *J Therm Anal Calorim* 122, 307–314. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-015-4670-5>
- Mohan, D., Singh, K.P., Singh, V.K., 2006. Trivalent chromium removal from wastewater using low cost activated carbon derived from agricultural waste material and activated carbon fabric cloth. *J Hazard Mater* 135, 280–295. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JHAZMAT.2005.11.075>
- Plazinski, W., Rudzinski, W., Plazinska, A., 2009. Theoretical models of sorption kinetics including a surface reaction mechanism: A review. *Adv Colloid Interface Sci.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2009.07.009>
- Revellame, E.D., Fortela, D.L., Sharp, W., Hernandez, R., Zappi, M.E., 2020. Adsorption kinetic modeling using pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order rate laws: A review. *Clean Eng Technol* 1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CLET.2020.100032>
- Rojas, A., Velásquez, E., Garrido, L., Galotto, M.J., López de Dicastillo, C., 2020. Design of active electrospun mats with single and core-shell structures to achieve different curcumin release kinetics. *J Food Eng* 273, 109900. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2019.109900>
- Rojas, A., Velásquez, E., Piña, C., Galotto, M.J., López de Dicastillo, C., 2021. Designing active mats based on cellulose acetate/polycaprolactone core/shell structures with different release kinetics. *Carbohydr Polym* 261, 117849. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2021.117849>
- Rudzinski, W., Plazinski, W., 2007. Studies of the kinetics of solute adsorption at solid/solution interfaces: On the possibility of distinguishing between the diffusional and the surface reaction kinetic models by studying the pseudo-first-order kinetics. *Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 111, 15100–15110. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp073249c>
- Saadi, R., Saadi, Z., Fazaeli, R., Fard, N.E., 2015. Monolayer and multilayer adsorption isotherm models for sorption from aqueous media. *Korean Journal of Chemical Engineering.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11814-015-0053-7>
- Shafigullin, L.N., Romanova, N. V., Gumerov, I.F., Gabrakhmanov, A.T., Sarimov, D.R., 2018. Thermal properties of polypropylene and polyethylene blends (PP/LDPE), in: *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering.* Institute of Physics Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/412/1/012070>

- Starkweather, H.W., Zoller, P., Jones, G.A., 1983. The Heat of Fusion of Poly(ethylene Terephthalate). *Journal of polymer science. Part A-2, Polymer physics* 21, 295–299. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pol.1983.180210211>
- Wang, J., Guo, X., 2020. Adsorption kinetic models: Physical meanings, applications, and solving methods. *J Hazard Mater* 390, 122156. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.122156>
- Wang, J., Liu, X., Liu, G., Zhang, Z., Wu, H., Cui, B., Bai, J., Zhang, W., 2019. Size effect of polystyrene microplastics on sorption of phenanthrene and nitrobenzene. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf* 173, 331–338. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.02.037>
- Zhang, C., Lan, Q., Zhai, T., Nie, S., Luo, J., Yan, W., 2018. Melt crystallization behavior and crystalline morphology of Polylactide/Poly(ϵ -caprolactone) blends compatibilized by lactide-caprolactone copolymer. *Polymers (Basel)* 10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym10111181>
- Zhang, J., Chen, H., He, H., Cheng, X., Ma, T., Hu, J., Yang, S., Li, S., Zhang, L., 2020. Adsorption behavior and mechanism of 9-Nitroanthracene on typical microplastics in aqueous solutions. *Chemosphere* 245, 125628. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHEMOSPHERE.2019.125628>